

QUALITY OF SCHOOL TEACHER'S IN INDONESIA: PLS APPROACH

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7528964>

Published Date: 12-January-2023

Abstract: The Government of Indonesia's efforts to improve the quality of teachers are carried out by issuing Law no. 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers. In ensuring the importance of the teacher's role in realizing the state's educational goals, efforts such as improving the role of teachers to become better professionals are needed both at the national and international levels. Correlation of the needs analysis construct with its indicators has a higher value than the correlation of indicators of skills, knowledge and changes in behavior. The correlation of skill constructs with their indicators has a higher value than the correlation of indicators. Analysis of needs, knowledge and changes in behavior. The correlation of the cautious construct with its indicator has a higher value than the correlation of extraversion, easy to get along, neurotic and open indicators. The extraversion construct with its indicator has a higher value than the correlation indicator of being careful, easy to get along with, neurotic and open. The construct that is easy to get along with its indicators has a higher value than the correlation indicators of caution, extraversion, neuroticism and openness. The construct of professional competence with its indicators has a higher value than the correlation of personality competence, pedagogic competence and social competence. The social competence construct with its indicators has a higher value than the correlation of personality competence, pedagogic competence and professional competence.

Keywords: Education, Training, Quality, State Junior High School Teachers.

1. INTRODUCTION

Pensijilan through portfolio assessment is given to teachers who have a bachelor or diploma IV (D-IV) or who have not met the requirements but have reached the age of 50 years or have work experience for 20 years, have group IV / a or meet a cumulative credit score along with class IV/a and was appointed to the teacher before December 30, 2005. This portfolio assessment is an acknowledgment of the teacher's professional experience in the form of an assessment document that describes academic eligibility (a) education and training (b) teaching design and implementation (c) supervisor and supervisor assessment (d) academic achievement (e) professional development work (f) participation in scientific forums (g) organizational and educational experience (h) relevant to education (Republic of Indonesia, 2011).

The provision of pensijilan through teacher professional training education (PLPG) is given to teachers who are not willing for portfolio assessment, fail to pass portfolio assessment and vice versa and do not meet the requirements for direct educator pensijilan (Republik Indonesia, 2011). Teachers who are allowed to take part in the PLPG are teachers who were appointed before 2016 and have a teacher competency exam (UKG) decision before the PLPG with the lowest score of 55. At the end of the PLPG. Materials reviewed in the PLPG include material depth, student-centred learning, teaching practices and achievement tests. Teachers are expected to pass the PLPG if they get the lowest score of 80. For teachers who do not pass the PLPG proficiency test, they may take four examinations for two years after carrying out free studies without going through the PLPG process (Republik Indonesia, 2016).

The provision of an educator certificate is directly given to teachers who have the qualifications of S2 or S3 education in the field of education or the field of recitation that are relevant to the subjects they teach and have the lowest class IV / b or meet the cumulative credit score equivalent to group IV / b or to teachers who have group IV/c or have a cumulative credit score equivalent to group IV/c (Republic of Indonesia, 2012).

The provision of an educator certificate through the Teacher Professional Education (PPG) pattern is given to teachers who have the qualifications of undergraduate education (S1) or D-IV and have been appointed as teachers until the end of 2015. The Teacher Professional Education Program is an educational program held after the undergraduate or graduate program. After being declared graduated from the PPG program, the teacher is entitled to an educator certificate (Republik Indonesia, 2017).

Therefore, the study of teacher quality is a matter that needs to be done. With so many phenomena that describe teacher evangelism not as expected, this study would like to dig deeper into why this may happen. The failure of teacher certification in improving the quality of teachers in Indonesia is certainly a concern, but there must be concrete efforts so that this program that has swallowed a large budget does not go to waste. For this reason, it is very important to try to improve the quality of teachers by minimizing the things that may hinder them (Mohd Nasrun, Mohd Nazaruddin & Ibrahim Siti Halipah, 2015).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary, quality means a good or bad rating of something (Language, 2001), so that the better something is, the better its quality is, on the other hand, the worse something is, the worse the quality. According to Juran (1993), quality is the suitability of product use (fitness for use) to meet customer needs and satisfaction.

The suitability of using a product is if the product has a long shelf life, improves the image or status of consumers who use it, is not easily damaged, has quality assurance and is ethical when used. Especially for services, it requires friendly, polite and honest customer service so that it can delight or satisfy customers (Yusoff, Ngah, Talib & Rahman, 2016; Mohd Nazaruddin, Azlizan & Siti Maisarah, 2015).

Crosby (1979), explains that quality, namely conformance to requirements, is in accordance with what is required or standardized. A product has quality if it matches the quality standards that have been set. Quality standards include raw materials, creation processes and finished products (Yusoff, Nawi & Ibrahim, 2015). For Deming (1982), quality is conformity to market needs. If Juran defines quality as fitness for use and Crosby as conformance to requirements, so Deming defines quality as conformity to market or consumer needs, the industry must really be able to master what consumers need for a product to be produced (Mohd Nazaruddin et al, 2020).

Feigenbaum (1986) commented that quality is full customer satisfaction. A product is said to be of quality if it is able to provide complete satisfaction to consumers, which is in accordance with what consumers expect of a product. Meanwhile, for Garvin (1988) quality is a dynamic condition related to products, people/labor, processes and tasks, and areas that meet or exceed customer or consumer expectations. Consumers' tastes or expectations for a product are always changing so that the quality of the product must also change or be adjusted. With the change in product quality, it takes a change or increase in workforce skills, changes in the creation process and tasks, and changes in industrial areas so that products can meet or exceed consumer expectations (Mohd. Nazaruddin, 2020).

It has been explained above that the quality of a teacher can be seen from the competencies he has. There are 4 competencies that must be possessed by a teacher, namely pedagogic competence, professional competence, social competence and personal competence. Referring to Spencer and Spencer (2001) argue that competence is a basic characteristic of a person related to the performance of efficient and superior criteria in a job in a certain atmosphere. Competence is said to be an underlying characteristic because character is a deep and attached part of a person's character and can predict various types of situations and jobs. Competence creates or predicts attitudes and performance. Competence really predicts who performs well or poorly, based on certain criteria or standards (Muhsin, Mohd. Nazaruddin & Nor Suzylah, 2021).

Competence as well as ability, is the capacity of a person to do various tasks on a job. A person's expertise is influenced by two things, namely intellectual skills and physical skills (Muhsin & Mohd. Nazaruddin, 2021; Robbins, 2004). Meanwhile, referring to the Decree of the Minister of National Education Number 045/U/2002, it is stated that

competence is a set of intelligent actions, full of responsibility that is owned by a person and is a condition that is considered capable of carrying out tasks in certain fields of work. According to McShane & Glinow (2008) skills are skills, knowledge, talents, values, direction and other personal characteristics that lead to superior achievement.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is in the form of quantitative descriptive and inference using cross-sectional method. According to Chua (2006), a quantitative study that uses cross-sectional methods with statistical data collection and measurement will produce reliable decisions. This is because investigations using numerical analysis methods emphasize the accuracy of evidence in a study (Chua, 2006).

This approach also uses a cross-sectional study approach where this study is carried out in a short period of time. Although it is said that long-term studies are better able to answer research questions more precisely, the cross-sectional method is used because of the time constraints encountered in the study. Patton (2005) explains that quantitative methods are suitable for use for a short period of time because they are able to explain a phenomenon that applies systematically, skillfully, easily processed and analyzed and can be stated in a short period of time.

Various methods may be used to cite data in an investigation, such as interviews, research questions (whether sent by post, hand or by email), reviews and so on (Sekaran, 2000). This study uses a review method through an inquiry form to cite data to answer all study questions. According to Mohd. Majid (1990), the review method is a way to collect data, including data that summarizes the act of knowing and responding quickly and easily to obtain the data in a short period of time. This method of review is also able to obtain information that states the actual situation of a case related to a population in its own context. The questions stated at the beginning of a study will be answered with the information obtained. The advantage of the review method is that it can cover a large sample (Mohd Majid, 1990), is more effective and efficient because of the large number of samples (Azizi, 2006), is easy and fast to circulate and saves costs and time (Mohd Sheffie, 1991).

Descriptive statistics and hypothesis testing were used in the design of this study. Descriptive statistics will look at the demographic factors of the respondents and the stages of the variables studied. Hypothesis testing was also used to examine the relationship between education and training and quality and the impression of personal simplification and work design on the relationship between education and training and quality. This study was carried out in a natural work environment.

4. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In this discussion, the researcher only uses the teacher quality variable to measure the achievement of the results of this study. So the researchers used the PLS 5 model in describing the research results model.

Figure I: PLS Model 5

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 1, pp: (43-49), Month: January - February 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

From the picture above, it can be seen that the correlation between item/indicator scores and construct scores. Individual indicators are considered reliable if they have a correlation value > 0.60, this can be seen in the table below:

Table I: Loading Factor Value Teacher Quality Variable (Y)

	Kompetensi Kepribadian	Kompetensi Pedagogik	Kompetensi Profesional	Kompetensi Sosial
Y.1		0,654		
Y.10	0,668			
Y.11	0,809			
Y.12	0,860			
Y.13	0,811			
Y.14	0,815			
Y.15				0,879
Y.16				0,909
Y.17			0,774	
Y.18			0,792	
Y.19			0,834	
Y.2		0,738		
Y.20			0,722	
Y.3		0,710		
Y.4		0,739		
Y.5		0,759		
Y.6		0,739		
Y.7		0,726		
Y.8		0,684		
Y.9		0,737		

Based on the outer loading in the table above, it shows that all indicators in the Education and training variable have a factor loading value greater than 0.60, this means that indicators with a loading value greater than 0.60 have a high level of validity and meet convergent validity so that all indicators in this study can be used.

Table II: Value of Loading Construct Teacher Quality Variable

	Nilai Outer Loading	Detail
Y.1	0,654	Achieve convergent validity
Y.10	0,668	Achieve convergent validity
Y.11	0,809	Achieve convergent validity
Y.12	0,860	Achieve convergent validity
Y.13	0,811	Achieve convergent validity
Y.14	0,815	Achieve convergent validity
Y.15	0,879	Achieve convergent validity
Y.16	0,909	Achieve convergent validity
Y.17	0,774	Achieve convergent validity
Y.18	0,792	Achieve convergent validity
Y.19	0,834	Achieve convergent validity
Y.2	0,738	Achieve convergent validity
Y.20	0,722	Achieve convergent validity
Y.3	0,710	Achieve convergent validity
Y.4	0,739	Achieve convergent validity
Y.5	0,759	Achieve convergent validity
Y.6	0,739	Achieve convergent validity
Y.7	0,726	Achieve convergent validity
Y.8	0,684	Achieve convergent validity
Y.9	0,737	Achieve convergent validity

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After the outer loading constructs that have a value less than 0.60 are dropped and then re-calculated, the evaluation model is obtained as shown below. The following is a picture of the evaluation of the convergent validity test model after it was modified, namely by removing the outer loading which is less than 0.60.

Table III: Evaluation Model

	Personality	Pedagogic	Professional	Social
Y.1	0,377	0,654	0,503	0,243
Y.10	0,668	0,514	0,464	0,427
Y.11	0,809	0,434	0,531	0,537
Y.12	0,860	0,496	0,596	0,648
Y.13	0,811	0,434	0,498	0,574
Y.14	0,815	0,479	0,536	0,587
Y.15	0,629	0,362	0,464	0,879
Y.16	0,627	0,465	0,607	0,909
Y.17	0,584	0,531	0,774	0,549
Y.18	0,481	0,574	0,792	0,405
Y.19	0,531	0,623	0,834	0,465
Y.2	0,512	0,738	0,636	0,411
Y.20	0,472	0,543	0,722	0,469
Y.3	0,449	0,710	0,562	0,352
Y.4	0,429	0,739	0,474	0,290
Y.5	0,435	0,759	0,532	0,334
Y.6	0,426	0,739	0,525	0,416
Y.7	0,411	0,726	0,483	0,327
Y.8	0,362	0,684	0,427	0,257
Y.9	0,428	0,737	0,554	0,372

From the table above, it can be seen that the correlation of the construct of personality competence with its indicators has a higher value than the correlation of pedagogic competence, professional competence and social competence. The construct of pedagogic competence with its indicators has a higher value than the correlation of personality competence, professional competence and social competence. The construct of professional competence with its indicators has a higher value than the correlation of personality competence, pedagogic competence and social competence. The social competence construct with its indicators has a higher value than the correlation of personality competence, pedagogic competence and professional competence.

4. CONCLUSION

The conclusion in this study is that discriminant validity is related to the principle that different constructs (manifest variables) should not correlate with high. The way to test discriminant validity with reflexive indicators is to see the crossloading value for each variable must be > 0.70. Correlation of the needs analysis construct with its indicators has a higher value than the correlation of indicators of skills, knowledge and changes in behavior. The correlation of skill constructs with their indicators has a higher value than the correlation of indicators. Analysis of needs, knowledge and changes in behavior. The correlation of the construct of knowledge with its indicators has a higher value than the correlation of indicators. Analysis of needs, skills and changes in behavior. And the correlation of the construct of attitude and behavior change with the indicator has a higher value than the correlation indicator. Analysis of needs, skills and knowledge. Thus, it can be concluded that all latent constructs or variables predict indicators in their block better than indicators in other blocks.

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